

Extreme Gravity Fields and Equation of Gravity Field. Astrophysical Aspects

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Abstract

A long enough interaction between a matter and a gravity field leads to considerable increase of the latter and to emergence of gravity field energy flux in the direction of matter acceleration. This is a direct consequence of the conservation law of energy-momentum. There have been obtained metrics of a spherically symmetric stationary gravity field, one of which corresponds to the Schwarzschild metric. The second metric corresponds to a static massless body with an expulsive field. The size of such a “bubble” is proportional to its energy. By pushing any matter out, the bubble obtains additional energy and grows. Most probably, this process is responsible for the formation of the irregular Universe and its accelerated expansion.

Keywords: Gravity, Bubbles, General Relativity Theory, Equation of Gravity Field, Conservation Law, Spherically Symmetric Fields, Dark Energy.

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1. Introduction

Einstein's gravity theory looks perfect and its results comparison with available manifestations of gravity fields confirms its correctness. Along with it, well known are its shortages, too: the energy problem, the problem of singularities, the problem of causality and the transition difficulties to the quantum gravitation. Despite the fact that a considerable part of observations can be explained based on a number of disconnected hypotheses, yet, there is no satisfactory picture explaining the observational data in great scales and in area of high energies.

Attempts of the principles revising, on which the theory was built up were unsuccessful. That is why we shall abide to these principles. We shall highlight only the natural necessity of use of the gravity field energy as a source of a gravity field, which principle was put forward by Einstein in 1913 [1] literally in the following words:

“It is possible to see that along with components of the energy-tensions tensor of a matter T_{ik} as field sources of equal value, also components of gravity field tensor act (namely θ_{ik}); evidently, this requirement is necessary as a gravitational action of a system cannot depend on a physical nature of the energy being the field source”. [1]

The dramatic story of a search of a covariant equation of gravity field lasted two years [2]. As a result, for obtaining an acceptable generally covariant equation of gravity field, it was necessary to abandon the field energy as the field source. The waiving of the field energy use in the Einstein's equation was justified by the negligible energy of the gravity field. In the well-known manual by Landau and Lifshitz ([3], p. 95), the absence of an energy of the gravitational-in-action S is explained as follows: “Gravitational interaction plays a role only for bodies with a big enough mass (due to the smallness of the gravitational constant). That is why, while studying a gravity field, usually, we have to deal with macroscopic bodies”. However a simple assessment of a correction of the field energy to the Newtonian gravity law leads to a correction comparable with the Schwarzschild's solution [4].

Now is not sure that the familiar Einstein's equation works satisfactorily in extreme gravity fields and not only in extremely great ones but also in ones connected with extremely large scales

of space and time. It is possible to select matching metric tensor of a spherically symmetric field of a point mass in by-passing of the Einstein's equation, however, while following all the principles of the general relativity theory and the principle of compliance to the Schwarzschild's solution in small fields.

A reader should not consider this paper as an alternative to the general relativity theory. Below we discuss a possibility of gravitational problems solving without the aid of the Einstein's equation – while the Einstein's equation itself is used for finding a full tensor of energy-momentum-tensions from a metric tensor.

2. Energy of gravity field and energy of matter

Already in the Newtonian theory, we are obliged to assign energy to a gravity field; and in this connection, if we chose the zero level of energy in conditions of a field absence, always its energy is negative.

Let us evaluate an energy exchange between a field with the strength α and a dust-like matter with the density ρ . If a flux of energy from outside is equal to zero, the energy density of the matter is equal to

$$\varepsilon_m = \sqrt{(\rho c^2)^2 + (c\rho\alpha t)^2}.$$

The field energy density [3] is equal to

$$\varepsilon_f = -\frac{\alpha^2}{8\pi G} = -k\alpha^2.$$

If energy densities of both matter and field are homogeneous in a given volume and besides, a flux of energy is absent from outside, the sum of these densities is constant. Let us consider the simplest case that this sum of densities is equal to zero²:

$$\varepsilon_m + \varepsilon_f = 0.$$

In this case, the field energy density grows in absolute value monotonously and unlimitedly. This is true as far as the condition is conserved of the field and matter uniformity, while a flux of energy from outside is absent. Now we are able to

² It was considered here that energy of a gravity field is extremely low. This is incorrect. For example, the energy density of the gravity field on the surface of Earth is comparable to the density of the entire energy of the air.

evaluate the time, within which the field energy will be comparable to the matter energy. If at an initial instant of time the following is true $\varepsilon(0)_f = -\rho c^2$, the time, after which the field energy would be doubled, is equal to

$$T = \sqrt{\frac{3}{16\rho\pi G}} \approx 3 \times 10^4 \rho^{-\frac{1}{2}}.$$

This quite special symmetric case allows obtaining nothing else but an idea of the time, after which energy densities of both field and energy are doubled. It is clear that in conditions of dispersed space and weak fields, we shall deal with very large values of time T . Along with it, it is necessary to have volumes with the radiuses $R \sim cT$ in order that the uniformity of the field and the dust had no time to be destroyed somehow note-worthily.

Figure 1. Active giant elliptical galaxy M87. Relativistic jet, which, probably, is accelerated by gravity field and dispersed on gas-dust cloud. (This Hubble Space Telescope photograph shows the jet of matter ejected from M87 at nearly the speed of light, as it stretches 1.5 kpc (5 kly) from the galactic core) [5, 6].

The momentum conservation law in processes of matter acceleration results in transferring of momentum (energy flux) to the gravity field. Just in the case with the energy density, both values grow on absolute value. As energy density is negative, the direction of the energy flux of the gravity field will coincide with the direction of the matter flux.

The reverse process - the process of weakening the gravitational field is possible only if the substance moves towards the force of gravity. For example, in the explosion of a heavy body or in the event that a clot of a pushing field acquires a significant momentum and meets in its path the substance, Figure (1).

So the matter acceleration in a gravity field of high strength or/and in largely extended fields results in an essential gravity field strength growth and in a field motion in direction of its action. It is not too difficult to see that via these processes, a matter formation is performed [7]. As in certain conditions, a collapse, an accretion or large-scale gas-dust clouds generate energy/matter exceeding their initial energy, we see that here the Einstein's equation can be a source of a considerable error.

3. Metric of gravity field of localized mass

The relativity principle states that a local light velocity measured with time and length standards (that are also local) does not depend on the local reference system and is isotropic [8]. Nevertheless from the point of view of a distant observer, the light velocity can depend on spatial coordinates, so this observer will see a light refraction.

It was noticed by Einstein and Fokker [9] that a system with a constant local velocity is described by the metric of the following kind:

$$ds^2 = v(c^2 dt^2 - dx^2 - dy^2 - dz^2),$$

Notably, $v > 0$ is a function of the coordinates².

Also to Einstein, the non-demanded result belongs obtained by him in his early paper in 1907 [9]. Einstein found the exact ratio connecting time in points of uniformly accelerated system

$$\tau = \tau_0 \exp \frac{\alpha \xi}{c^2},$$

where ξ is a distance between points and α is an acceleration of the system. It means that for any continuous field in the limit of small ξ , the following is true:

$$g_{00} = \exp \frac{2\varphi}{c^2} \approx 1 + \frac{2\varphi}{c^2}.$$

² Authors [8] performed speculations, where from this result they came to the Nordstrom's generally covariant equation. However, the Nordstrom's scalar theory did not withstand the competition with the general relativity theory.

If to follow these results for a stationary spherically symmetric field, its metric in spatially isotropic coordinates will be

$$ds^2 = \exp\left[\frac{2\psi(r)}{c^2}\right] (c^2 dt^2 - dr^2 - r^2 d\theta^2 - r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\varphi^2). \quad (2)$$

This is sufficient to find the metric of the field of a localized mass. According to the correspondence principle in a limit of weak stationary field, the following is true:

$$\frac{2\psi(r)}{c^2} \rightarrow -\frac{r_g}{r}$$

where $r_g = \frac{2GM}{c^2}$ is Schwarzschild radius. The obtained metric

$$ds^2 = \exp\left(-\frac{r_g}{r}\right) (c^2 dt^2 - dr^2 - r^2 d\theta^2 - r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\varphi^2) \quad (3)$$

has absolutely no similarity to the Schwarzschild's metric and yet, it describes the observed effects in moderate fields exactly in the same values as the Schwarzschild's metric does. The reason for this is the asymptotic equality of Christoffels essential symbols being parts of the motion equation. Important here is the fact that the gravity force acceleration obtained from the metric (3) is asymptotically equal to that obtained from the Schwarzschild's metric. Indeed, we can compare the free fall acceleration

$$\bar{a}_r = -\frac{GM}{r^2} e^{\frac{GM}{c^2 r}}, \quad (4)$$

found based on the metric (3) with the corresponding result obtained by Schwarzschild:

$$\bar{a}_r = -\frac{GM}{r^2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - 2GM/(rc^2)}} \approx -\frac{GM}{r^2} e^{\frac{GM}{c^2 r}}.$$

In Figure (2), we see that these field tensions differ visibly from each other only close to the Schwarzschild's radius, for example on surfaces of neutron stars. In area of strong fields close to localized masses, a field tension (4) grows extremely fast, actually quicker than any exponential function. Most probably, gravitational waves being generated at mergegence of massive space objects will allow finding out, which of gravity law versions – (3) or (4) – is realized in these phenomena.

4. Equation of gravity field and another static solution

Let us pay attention to the fact that also the product of two metrics of the kind of (2) belongs to (2), i.e. the metrics form a group on multiplication. This allows – based on knowing of several solutions – finding their superposition by multiplying of the metrics.

Of no less importance is the fact that the parameter ψ forms a group on addition. This is important because now we can put forward the following simple generally covariant equation³:

Figure 2. Dependence of gravity force on distance from a point mass: Newtonian law – dashed line; Schwarzschild solution – dash-and-dot line; exact solution – solid line. In the rectangle, the stretched fifty times graph part is shown. [10]

$$\square \psi = -4\pi G \sum_j T_{jj}. \quad (5)$$

With due consideration of the equation solution (2), the sought-after metric will be in a general case as follows:

$$ds^2 = \exp\frac{2\psi}{c^2} \eta_{ik} dx_i dx_k, \quad (6)$$

Notably, η_{ik} is a linear element of a flat space.

The above-said does not mean at all that Einstein's equation needed to be withdrawn from circulation. If T_{ik} is the full tensor of energy-

³From the formal point of view, the equation (5) is equivalent to the equation of the Nordstrom's first scalar theory [11], notwithstanding that here the parameter ψ of the metric (6) coincides with a potential only in the limit of weak fields.

momentum including both matter and gravity field, it is possible to connect it with the metric tensor with aid of the equality

$$T_{ik} = \frac{c^4}{8\pi G} G_{ik}. \quad (7)$$

This is nothing else than the reversion of the Einstein's equation in its primeval appearance [1] meeting all the principles of the general relativity theory.

In particular, from (5) and (6), the uniform field metric is found:

$$ds^2 = e^{\frac{2\alpha x}{c^2}} (c^2 dt^2 - dx^2 - dy^2 - dz^2),$$

from which from the equation (7), we find the tensor of energy-momentum of a uniform field

$$\tau_{ik} = \frac{\alpha^2}{8\pi G} \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

5. Stationary spherically symmetric solution in "empty" space

In a stationary case in an empty space, the equation (5) is transformed to the Laplace's equation

$$\Delta\psi = 0,$$

which – in spherical coordinates – has the very well known solution $\psi = \frac{C_1}{r} + C_2$ and gives two solutions of the Schwarzschild's problem. One of those solutions gives the metric (3), while another one is

$$ds^2 = \exp\left(\frac{r}{r_0}\right) (c^2 dt^2 - dr^2 - r^2 d\theta^2 - r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\varphi^2) \quad (8)$$

In this case, the gravity field (the gravity force) is directed outwards:

$$\bar{\alpha}_r = \frac{G\mu}{r^2} e^{-\frac{G\mu}{c^2 r}}. \quad (9)$$

The field (9) is represented by a smooth function including the area at the origin of the coordinates. Furthermore, in the limit $r \rightarrow 0$, the field becomes equal to zero, Figure (3). Here there is no need in presumption of presence of a negative mass, which would be utmost incredible. The scalar incurvature of the metric (6) at the origin of the

coordinates is equal to zero as in the middle of this body, there is no mass. The parameter of mass dimensionality μ can take any positive values, Figure (3). In a distant area, the tension approximates to the Newtonian law with the only difference that this field of such *gravitational bubble* has the opposite direction. The field energy can be found from the equation (7). It coincides with the field energy in the Newtonian approximation $-\frac{\alpha^2}{8\pi G}$, which allows calculating the entire energy of this object:

$$U = -\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{1}{8\pi G} \int \alpha^2 dV = -\frac{\mu c^2}{2}.$$

Here the value $-\frac{1}{2}\mu$ plays role of a negative mass of a gravity field.

The expression (16) has its extreme value in the point

$$r_0 = \frac{G\mu}{2c^2} = 3.7128 \times 10^{-28} \mu,$$

This value is proportional to the "mass", Figure (3). If in this point r_0 , the field tension is α_{max} , it is possible to connect these values via a dimensionless constant not connected with the gravitational constant,

$$\frac{r_0 \alpha_{max}}{c^2} = \frac{2}{e^2} = 0.27067.$$

Thus, the gravitational bubble has the "size" r_0 linearly dependent on its full energy but inversely proportional to a module of maximum field tension.

In a center of a gravitational bubble, a kern is situated, which is represented by a ground with almost zero field (see Figure (3)). Notably, the kern potential is little different (if any) from upside potential at the origin of the coordinates

$$\Phi_0 = \int_0^\infty \frac{G\mu}{r^2} e^{-\frac{G\mu}{c^2 r}} dr = c^2.$$

The potential Φ of the kern plateau is close to the limiting value c^2 . This means that an electromagnetic signal emitted from a distant point will have its frequency arbitrarily close to zero. And vice versa, sources located on the kern on a sufficient distance from its center will be observed as sources of extremely hard radiation.

Figure 3. Vacuum solutions for expulsive field in cases of different “masses” of gravitational field. [10]

Particles and macroscopic bodies, while *falling* from the gravitational bubble, acquire a relativistic velocity. Along with it, the negative gravitational energy of the bubble grows on an absolute value; the bubble becomes unstable. The next stable state is a bubble of a greater size, so the bubble grows, Figure (4). So the gravitational bubble is a source of both energy and matter, in what connection the energy conservation law remains in force as the energy acquired by the matter is compensated by the negative energy of the gravity field.

Figure 4. Evolution of the gravitational bubble. The ejection of matter increases the energy of matter, the law of energy conservation requires an increase in the

absolute value of the energy of the gravitational field, i.e. bubble increases. Quasi-static model. [10]

Natural expectants for gravitational bubbles role are *Fermi's bubbles*, Figure (5). It is hard to find another more reasonable explanation, how it is possible that a transparent object can emit the hard gamma rays.

Most likely, various objects with their common name "bubbles" possess the same nature. In this case, the formation of shock waves and turbulence (Crab Nebula).

These processes are associated with the formation of matter. The law of energy conservation is fulfilled due to the replenishment of negative gravitational energy.

For weak gravity fields, it is possible to replenish the static and quasi-static solutions by a linear combination of known solutions. Also it is possible to suppose a development of objects featured with an expulsive field and growing due to a matter extrusion (see Section 2). Most probably, the gravitational bubbles are formed in a course of a collapse of massive space objects as along with this process, a matter acquires great energy, while a relevant gravitational field acquires the same energy of the opposite sign. The appearance of remains of supernovas confirms it to some extent.

6. Conclusions

It is possible to imagine an ever-growing bubble brought into coincidence with the visible part of the Universe. The visible red shift can be assigned to “childish pranks” of this bubble, when it was growing due to the matter extrusion. If this is the case and we are situated on a plateau of a super-bubble, the gravitational potential is close to the possible maximum. Then we should observe consequences of this phenomenon as the Doppler's red shift strengthened by the gravitational shift in a distant area. Even farther, perhaps, the red shift is so great that we perceive the “overseas” part of the Universe as a microwave “relic” radiation.

Figure 5. The Fermi space satellite, flying in orbit around the Earth, discovered unusual huge structures in the center of our Galaxy. Near the center of the galaxy there are two huge bubbles (red and white spots in the photo). The plane of the Milky Way runs horizontally through the center of the picture [12, 13].

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